

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIAL. PARCHMENT GLUTAMINE INDEX (PQI): A NOVEL METHOD TO ESTIMATE GLUTAMINE DEAMIDATION LEVELS IN PARCHMENT COLLAGEN OBTAINED FROM LOW-QUALITY MALDI-TOF DATA

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Supplementary figure 1: Histogram of extent of deamidation (q) for the 8 peptides.

Supplementary figure 2: Histogram of Parchment Glutamine Index (PQI). Although theoretically the value of PQI ranges from zero to one, 54% of the values are above one due to the problem of accurate baseline correction.